

Reactions at the Surface of Hot Metallic Filaments.

Part II. The Reaction $\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ on Platinum-iridium Alloys.

By B. S. SRIKANTAN.

In Part I the interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen on the surface of platinum has been described. The present paper presents the results of the experiments with platinum-iridium alloys used as catalysts. Alloys containing 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 per cent. of iridium have been used. The object of the investigation was to study if the composition of the alloy or the nature of the surface is responsible for the activity. Incidentally it was thought that these experiments would throw some light on the nature of promoters or mixed catalysts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus and the experimental methods were the same as in the first part, except that a different method was adopted for the measurement of the temperature of the wire. The alloys are known to have a very low temperature coefficient of resistance and hence the calculation of the temperature from the data on resistance would be inaccurate. The temperature was measured with the aid of an optical pyrometer, specially constructed for the purpose.

The pyrometer was first calibrated with reference to pure platinum wire (whose temperature was known from its temperature coefficient of resistance), at various temperatures, against an accurate voltmeter across the pyrometer lamp. The glow of these wires, when in use, was matched with the filament of the pyrometer and the voltmeter readings taken. With the help of the volt-temperature graph, the temperature of the wire was obtained.

It must however be pointed out that this method of measuring temperature is not free from defects. There is a great deal of personal error in matching the intensity. Great difficulty was experienced due to slight differences in colour of the two glowing filaments, though their brightness was equal. To overcome this difficulty a piece of red glass was interposed on the observation side,

Moreover, the wire has to be observed through a layer of about 2 cms. of water (cf. Part I) the glass walls of the Dewar flask and the reaction vessel. Further there is always a thin film of moisture on the outer side of the Dewar vessel, for the water inside is at 0° and this thin film of moisture is persistent and could not be wiped off completely. All these factors contribute to give a lower value for the temperature than it actually is (cf. Retzow, *Z. Vereins. Deutsch. Ing.*, 1923, 67, 179). However care was taken to maintain the conditions similar in all the experiments involving the use of the optical pyrometer, which was itself calibrated under similar conditions. The Dewar vessel was surrounded on all sides except the observation side by means of a black paper in order to avoid all optical illusions arising out of the varying brightness of the room during the various seasons. The values are comparable among themselves. Within a fair degree of accuracy it is possible to say that the actual temperatures recorded might be about 2 per cent. in error in the neighbourhood of 1000°.

All the wires used in these experiments were as before 24 cm. long and 0.01 cm. in diameter.

The Results.

Platinum-iridium alloy containing 5 per cent. of iridium.—The wire was quite steady in activity and the data could be duplicated. The following tables give the results at various temperatures.

TABLE I.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 104.3 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100.4 \text{ mm.}$				Temperature = 870°.			
Time (sec.) ...	—	0	15	30	45	60	75	90	
Total press (mm.)	204.7	200.6	188.3	169.0	157.4	148.0	140.1	133.9	
Unimolecular constants ...	—	—	0.0133	0.0132	0.0132	0.0132	0.0132	0.0131	
							Mean	0.0132	

TABLE II.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 105.1 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 107.8 \text{ mm.}$		Temperature = 915°.				
Time (sec.)	—	0	10	20	30	40	
Total press (mm.)	...	212.9	198.9	176.6	161.8	149.4	140.9	
Unimolecular constants	—	—	0.0272	0.0252	0.0250	0.0242	
						Mean	0.0254	

Note:—The reaction is so rapid that it is not possible to raise the wire to the required temperature all at once. So a few seconds were taken to adjust the current till a balance was got in the bridge and hence the time is not noted in the above two tables at the beginning. The constants are calculated after the reading marked with an asterisk. It is just possible that this would interfere in the observation of any peculiarity in the initial stages of the reaction as in the case of platinum wire. But a careful experiment in Table III shows that with this wire there is no peculiarity in the initial stages.

TABLE III.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 102.5 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 112.8 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 930°.					
Time (sec.)	0	10	20	30	40	50
Total press. (mm.)	215.3	187.4	166.8	152.0	141.5	133.5
Unimolecular constants ...	—	0.0284	0.0281	0.0276	0.0267	0.0258	—
					Mean	0.0273	

The reaction in the above experiment was allowed to proceed till about 84 per cent. and the gas analysed.

TABLE IV.

Percentage of gases.	CO ₂	CO	H ₂	CH ₄
By calculation. ...	2.83	85.28	11.79	—
By analysis. ...	3.17	85.05	11.78	—

Hence in this reaction there seems to be no possibility of any other side reaction involving the production of methane.

The temperature over which the reaction could be studied is very limited. Below 850° the optical pyrometer is not very reliable and above 950° the reaction is too fast to be kept under control. The energy of activation calculated from the above data is 36,000 cal.

A microscopic study of the surface of wires before and after the reaction does not show prominent changes in the surface (*cf.* Plate I)

Platinum-iridium alloy containing 10 per cent. of iridium.—Unfortunately a systematic investigation of this wire could not be made, as the wire snapped due to an explosion caused by the introduction of oxygen into the gas mixture by mistake. The surface of the wire after this explosion presented a sintered appearance (*cf.* Plate II) and small beads had collected on the surface. The broken wire was spot welded by means of a tiny arc and a few experiments were carried out. Figure 1 gives the summary of the results obtained with this

wire at 935°. It is evident that the activity of the sintered catalyst is far lower than that of the fresh one. Perhaps the active centres which are responsible for strong adsorption of the reacting gases were destroyed due to the heating in the explosive mixture.

Fig. 1.

Platinum-iridium alloy with 15 per cent. of iridium.—The wire was steady in activity and the results were reproducible. The following tables give the velocity constants at various temperatures. A microscopic study of the surface before and after the experiments did not show any great change. It is similar to the 5 per cent. alloy (*cf.* Plate I).

TABLE V.

	$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 99.8 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 109.9 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 895°.				
Time (sec.) ...	0	150*	750	1050	1350	1650	1950
Total press (mm.)...	209.7	204.7	158.4	142.0	130.0	122.4	111.5
Unimolecular constants ...	—	—	0.00097	0.00101	0.00104	0.00097	0.00100
						Mean	0.00100

* Error in adjusting the temperature at first.

TABLE VI.

$P_{CO_2} = 99.7 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{H_2} = 103.5 \text{ mm.}$			Temperature = 935°.		
Time (sec.) ...	0	30*	60	90	120	150	180
Total press (mm.) ...	203.2	190.5	182.0	174.1	167.0	160.5	155.0
Unimolecular constants ...	—	—	0.00327	0.00331	0.00331	0.00331	0.00331
						Mean	0.00331
Pt-Ir wire (5%)						(Pt-Ir wire (10%))	

Before

After

After

Before

PLATE I.

PLATE II.

Pt Ir wire (20%)

After

PLATE III.

Before

* Temperature on the high side at first.

TABLE VII.

	$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 101.1 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 109.7 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 975°.				
Time (sec.)	0	15	45	75	105	135
Total press (mm.)	...	210.8	201.5	184.8	171.5	161.0	151.9
Unimolecular constants. ...	—	0.00591	0.00600	0.00591	0.00580	0.00580	
						Mean	0.00588

The following table gives the temperature coefficient and the energy of activation for the reaction on the surface of this wire.

TABLE VIII.

Temperature range.	Temperature coeff. for 10°.	Energy of activation.
895°—935°	1.35	83,000 cala.
935°—975°	1.15	43,000 „

The alloy with 5 per cent. of iridium is more active than the one containing 16 per cent. of iridium. At 930° the reaction rate at the surface of the 5 per cent. alloy is about eight times as that at the surface of the other. The temperature coefficient and the energy of activation for the reaction with the former is far lower than that of latter at about the same temperature range. This is in agreement with the idea that an active catalyst renders available the energy of activation at a far lower temperature than a comparatively poor catalyst. So it is not surprising that an increase in temperature lowers the temperature coefficient and the energy of activation at the surface of the 15 per cent. alloy.

It was observed that the wires containing 20, 25 and 30 per cent. of iridium were very unsteady in their activity. Their resistance and probably their surface also change with use. In all these cases it was noticed that when the bridge was balanced for one temperature, it was entirely different after a few experiments without any further adjustment of the balancing resistances of the bridge. A microscopic examination of the surfaces before and after the experiments shows that all these wires were affected more or less in the same way. Plate III gives an example.

Platinum-iridium alloy with 20 per cent. of iridium.—To start with, the wire was not steady in activity. The velocity coefficients

were not constant. But after a few experiments unimolecular velocity constants were obtained, though their values varied from experiment to experiment. In four experiments carried out in succession the velocity constants at 945° with 100 mm. of each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen were 0·00694, 0·00890, 0·00141, 0·00055 respectively. Perhaps this behaviour is due to the poisoning of the surface by carbon monoxide. So the wire was heated in vacuum for one minute at about 1000°. It was found that the resistance of the wire changed such that the temperature of the wire measured by the pyrometer was slightly higher than the previous value, without any change in the bridge coils. The velocity constant increased to 0·00089. Further heating in vacuum for a minute before the next experiment did not make any change in the temperature of the filament but the velocity constant of the reaction was slightly higher than the previous one. The following table gives a summary of the results of experiments carried out with 100 mm. of each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen at 960° and the wire being heated in vacuum for one minute at about 1000° before each experiment.

TABLE IX.

Experiment No.	75	76	77	78
Unimolecular velocity constant.	0·00089	0·00109	0·00207	0·00269
(mean value)				

TABLE X₂

Experiment No.	79	80	83	85
Unimolecular velocity constants.	0·00278	0·00337	0·00360	0·01050
(mean value)				

The progressive increase in the activity of the wire is perhaps due to the liberation of the adsorbed carbon monoxide every time the wire is heated in vacuum. Table X gives the results of a series of experiments carried out at 960° after heating the wire in vacuum for 5 minutes at about 1000° before each experiment.

The following table shows that if the wire was heated for a longer period (10 minutes) the activity is so increased that even at 865° the reaction is too fast to be measured.

TABLE XI.

[Heated the wire in vacuum for 10 mins.]

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 102.5$ mm. $P_{\text{H}_2} = 103.3$ mm. Temperature $\approx 865^\circ$.

Time (sec.)	0	15*	30	45	60
Total press. (mm.)	205.8	187.4	154.0	137.9	129.5
Press. of H ₂ (mm.)	103.3	84.9	51.5	35.4	27.0

Since it is very difficult to drive off the adsorbed carbon monoxide from the surface it was thought better to burn it off. So a small quantity of oxygen was introduced in the reaction mixture and the wire was burnt in it. But it was found that such a procedure lowered the activity of the wire to a great extent. While the reaction went to 70 per cent. in 60 seconds at 865° , after burning it in oxygen, the reaction went to only 50 per cent. in 360 seconds.

The results of gas analysis quoted in Table XII show that the reaction products are only carbon monoxide and water and that no other side-reaction is possible.

TABLE XII.

Experiment No.	Percentage composition.	CO ₂	CO	H ₂	CH ₄	
82	By calculation	22.52	53.33	24.15	—
	By analysis	22.05	55.37	22.87	Nil
90	By calculation	34.07	32.40	33.57	—
	By analysis	33.72	33.14	33.14	Nil

Platinum-iridium alloy with 25 per cent. of iridium.—This wire is also interesting in that its resistance changes with use, so that its temperature when first adjusted at 965° , fell to 925° without further adjustment; and again rose to 1105° by itself. But this wire gave for the velocity coefficients steady values. The resistance did not change in the middle of an experiment.

Table XIII gives a summary of few experiments carried out with this wire with 100 mm. of each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen.

TABLE XIII.

Experiment No.	...	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108
Temperature	...	965°	925°	985°	1025°	1050°	1065°	1075°	1100°
Unimolecular constants (mean value).		0.00188	0.00105	0.00202	0.00388	0.00350	0.00679	0.00748	0.00800

* The temperature was slightly on the lower side to start with.

In these experiments the possibility of the drift in the activity of the wire corresponding to changes in resistance has to be recognised. Hence the above data cannot be used to calculate the temperature coefficient of the reaction.

Platinum-iridium alloy with 30 per cent. of iridium.—This wire was found to be very active and in general behaved in the same way as the previous wire. The following table gives the data for the reaction at 1000°. Even when the temperature was lowered to 920° in the subsequent experiments the reaction rate did not fall down. In fact it was 25 per cent. faster than at 1000°. The reaction went to about 80 per cent. in a minute and a quarter. So further work with this wire was abandoned.

TABLE XIV.

$P_{CO_2} = 101.7$ mm.		$P_{H_2} = 101.6$ mm.		Temperature = 1000°.					
Time (sec.)	0	30*	45	60	75	90	105
Total press. (mm.)	...	203.3	169.5	149.1	133.3	123.3	117.5	113.6	
Unimolecular constants	...	—	—	0.0204	0.0226	0.0220	0.0228	0.0221	
							Mean	0.0221	

Summary and Conclusions.

1. The interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen has been studied at the surface of platinum-iridium alloys containing 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 per cent. of iridium.

2. The 5 per cent. alloy is more active than either the 10 or 15 per cent. alloy. The 30 per cent. alloy is the most active of all the catalysts and the reaction rate could not be controlled with any degree of accuracy for even at 920° the reaction went to 80 per cent. in a minute and a quarter. The activity does not seem to have any correlation with the composition of the alloys.

3. The temperature coefficient and the heats of activation have been calculated for the reaction with 5 and 15 per cent. alloys. The energy of activation with a powerful catalyst is lower than that with a poor catalyst at about the same temperature range.

* Temperature on the low side to start with.

4. It was observed that in the case of the 10 per cent. alloy the sintered surface is less active than an unsintered one.

5. The alloys containing 20, 25 and 30 per cent. of iridium change their activity with use. This is partly due to the strong and irreversible adsorption of carbon monoxide and partly due to the changes in the nature of the surface. In the case of the 20 per cent. alloy heating in vacuum improves the activity perhaps due to the *expulsion of carbon monoxide from the surface.*

6. The resistance of the wires (20, 25 and 30 per cent. alloys) changes slowly from experiment to experiment.

The surfaces of these wires have been examined microscopically before and after the experiments. The alloys with 20, 25 and 30 per cent. of iridium show more or less similar changes.

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DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

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